

FORMATION OF NEEDS AND WORKING ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: In this article, the increasing needs of preschool children and the formation of the characteristics of children's labor activity are highlighted.

Key words: Need, interest, personality, young age, social, work, intellect, play, labor, activity.

Nowadays, the needs of preschool children are increasing more and more. The reason for this is the great interest in the creation of technologies and education. So let's first understand what the desire is. Man, like all other organisms, always needs various things that exist in the environment outside of him in order to maintain his life. This human body's need for something causes craving. So, when we say need, we understand the need of our organism for something.

Young children (newborn children) mainly have organic needs (for example: eating, quenching thirst, bathing), in preschool children, in addition to such organic needs, the first buds of social and intellectual needs begin to appear. For example, preschool children are very curious, even if they cannot speak well yet. They don't rest until they can see everything in sight. This kind of curiosity found in children of preschool age indicates the emergence of intellectual abilities in them.

Social, intellectual and moral needs begin to be clearly seen in children of preschool age. If a child can sit alone with a toy for a long time, a child of preschool age (especially children of the middle and older groups) cannot tolerate such solitary play. Due to the fact that children have mastered their speech to a certain extent and are extremely mobile, they have a need to interact with adults and peers who are close to them. That is why children of preschool age cannot satisfy their needs with relationships within a narrow family and begin to strive for wider relationships. Now they play collectively with their neighbors' children. Thus, the spheres of social relations and activities of children of all ages will expand more and more.

One of the strong needs inherent in the nature of a child of preschool age is the need to learn everything. As the scope of the child's activities expands, the need to know the things around him also increases. The reason for this is his lack of life experience. Everything is new for the child and therefore, the child tries to learn it in every way. That's why he always asks countless questions.

It should also be mentioned that the kindergarten environment (that is, the order, discipline and various activities in it) creates conditions for the harmonious development of high social, intellectual, moral and hygienic needs of children. From the point of view of psychology, a habit is something close to a need, that is, our habits are so deeply ingrained that they become a need. That's why when we mean creating positive and useful needs in children, we mean educating them in positive and useful habits. Independent positive habits (needs) formed during preschool age remain throughout a person's life. The wise folk saying "A bird does

what it sees in its nest" is not just said. Preschool education organization is also considered as a second home for children. Whatever knowledge, skills and abilities they acquire here, and the habits they acquire, reflect on them throughout their lives.

Curiosity plays a big role in the life of preschool children and their mental growth. Interest, like desire, is one of the factors that motivates a child to do something. By interest, we understand a special desire to know things and events in reality a little deeper. So curiosity is a complex mental phenomenon related to the cognitive process. Preschool children are not equally interested in all things, and they are less interested in some things. But the interest of preschool children is not as fixed and stable as that of adults. Interests of children of this age are still not stable, they move from one thing to another very quickly.

The importance of interest for a child's development is that the child tries to learn as much as possible about what he is interested in and, therefore, does not get bored of doing what he is interested in for a long time. This, in turn, helps to develop and strengthen such important qualities as the child's attention and will. In addition, children's early interest in a field plays the role of a kind of preparation for them to occupy this field in the future. Most children of all ages have very diffuse and superficial interests. They are not interested in the essence or result of things and events, but only in these things and events. Therefore, it is necessary to strive to create unstable interests in children. Because the role of such interests in the learning process at school, that is, in mastering the basics of science, is huge. Another characteristic that should be formed in children is their work activity. Children's activities, which include labor activities, mainly start from preschool age. At this age, even if children's work is very simple and elementary, it is very important for their mental development. As a result of conversations with children of preschool age, children's positive attitude towards work, work is first manifested in children's games. Children do not limit themselves to copying the labor activities of adults in their games, but begin to take action to directly participate in the work of adults. For example, girls take part in carrying water while their mothers are doing laundry, washing some smaller things (tablecloths), cleaning and sweeping houses and yards, and boys tend to participate in the work done by their father. Children of this age are psychologically interested in the labor process itself, not the result of their work.[2]

Evaluating the work of preschool children plays a big role in educating them in a positive attitude towards work. It is a fact that children make many mistakes when they are doing what they can. But this means that children should not be involved in labor, and adults can do the work of children themselves. There is a proverb in the Eastern peoples: "Give the child a job, then run away." This is a very true and vital statement. This means that when children are given a task, they need to keep an eye on how they are doing it. Children, especially young children, do not yet have labor skills, hand muscles are not well developed. That's why children can drop and break something not intentionally or out of stupidity, but because they can't play. When such a "catastrophe" occurs, it is not appropriate to fight or put a child down saying "Anqov, Merov, can't you look me in the eye?" Instead, it is necessary to show the child how to perform this work. Organizing preschool children into a friendly team is of great importance in raising them in the spirit of hard work. When working as a team, the educator instructs each child to perform certain work. In this way, children work as a team.

For example: children of a large group work as a team. One child sets the table on the table, the second child puts spoons and forks, the third child puts chairs, and the fourth child puts bread

on the table. Children who have learned to be on duty in a preschool educational organization will also help in the family. In general, middle-aged and older children should be given work tasks that are sufficient for them in the family. This creates great opportunities for educating them in the spirit of hard work and for them to develop certain labor skills. It will be very difficult to attract a child who participates in socially useful work to work later.

The type of labor activities in which children are involved in the preschool education organization is very diverse. For example; taking care of animals or plants in the nature corner, working in the garden yard, being on duty in the kitchen and in the group, helping to dress the little ones, etc.

It should also be mentioned that young children are not yet able to start their own work. Therefore, they are engaged in very simple types of work, that is, watering plants, feeding fish, sprinkling water in the yard, etc. [1]

Children of the middle and older groups completely differentiate work from play and begin to treat it seriously. They understand the result of work, that is, the social essence of work, for whom and why it is necessary. They approach the household chores of adults with great enthusiasm, they make various toys for children from paper, cardboard and plasticine. Pedagogically correctly organized labor activity has a great impact on the comprehensive development of children in all aspects, both physically, mentally, aesthetically, and morally.

Kindergarten children are engaged in some kind of play, education, or work activity. The behavior of children of kindergarten age depends on the conditions in which they are implemented. They do not even understand the motives of behavior. That's why they often begin to perform one or another behavior in a certain situation, without giving a full report on their own.

At this age, children's actions and motives of behavior change and develop. Behavioral motives of adult children consist of fully realized motives. For example; the motives behind the actions and behaviors of older kindergarten children are similar to adults in all respects. Based on such a strong inclination, they organize imitation games, educational, that is, leadership training and labor training. The main goals of children are to strengthen interaction with adults. When children begin to establish good relations with adults, they try to fulfill the tasks ordered by adults and obey the rules of the established order.

During preschool age, the awareness of one's own value begins to emerge. When children come to kindergarten, they first try not to notice their tenkurs. Later, during various games and compulsory activities, they join the children's team and try to win the respect of their peers, that is, they strive to look good to other children in every way. The role of moral motives in the development of the motives of children's behavior in kindergarten is extremely important. As children become aware of their behavior, the role of motives for observing moral rules, that is, motives for observing social moral rules, becomes stronger. Children begin to learn to act from the point of view of social benefit, and not from their selfish interests. For example: children will give their favorite toys to other children and even share sweets they brought from home. In this way, children begin to develop social motives. Older kindergarten children always try to help younger children, that is, act on the basis of social motives.

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